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journal homepage: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf>**ISSUES OF ELECTRONIC ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE ACTIVITIES OF MEMBERS OF THE SUPERVISORY BOARD AT STATE ENTERPRISES****Tashmatov Rustam Xusanovich***Doctor of Economics.**Privatization and government Asset Management
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Email: rustam9837@mail.ru***ВОПРОСЫ ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ ОЦЕНКИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ЧЛЕНОВ НАБЛЮДАТЕЛЬНОГО СОВЕТА НА ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ****Ташматов Рустам Хусанович***Доктор экономических наук.**Приватизация и управление государственными активами
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электронная почта: rustam9837@mail.ru***DAVLAT KORXONALARIDA KUZATUV KENGASHI A'ZOLARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI ELEKTRON BAHOLASH MASALALARI****Tashmatov Rustam Xusanovich***Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori.**Xususiy lashtirish va Davlat aktivlarini boshqarish
Muammolarni o'rganish markazi, bo'lim boshlig'i.
elektron pochta: rustam9837@mail.ru***abstract**

This article presents the main methods and methods for assessing the effectiveness of the activities of members of the board of directors (supervisory board) at state-owned enterprises, summarizes the general rules and results of these assessments, and also gives suggestions for the possibility of using this practice in Uzbekistan.

аннотация

В данной статье приведены основные методы и приемы оценки эффективности деятельности членов совета директоров (наблюдательного совета) на предприятиях с государственным участием, обобщены общие положения и

результаты этих оценок, а также даны предложения по возможностям применения данной практики в Узбекистане.

annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada davlat ishtirokidagi korxonalarida direktorlar kengashi (kuzatuv kengashi) a'zolari faoliyati samaradorligini baholashning asosiy usullari va uslublari keltirilgan, ushbu baholashlarning umumiy qoidalari va natijalari umumlashtirilgan, shuningdek, ushbu amaliyotni O'zbekistonda qo'llash imkoniyatlari bo'yicha takliflar berilgan.

Keywords:

Board of directors (supervisory board), Code of Corporate Governance, Survey, interview, performance assessment.

Ключевые слова:

совет директоров (наблюдательный совет), кодекс корпоративного управления, анкета, интервью, оценка эффективности деятельности.

Kalit so'zlar:

direktorlar kengashi (kuzatuv kengashi), korporativ boshqaruv kodeksi, so'rovnomi, intervyu, faoliyat samaradorligini baholash.

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Introduction

The results of a study of foreign practice and experience in assessing the effectiveness of the board of directors (supervisory board) showed that the most effective way to conduct an assessment is the “initiative of certified directors” – a strict written and oral knowledge verification procedure introduced in the UK. This procedure is also widely used in Japanese corporations. Foreign companies use various methods and tools to assess the activities of the board of directors (supervisory board). To analyze the quality of the activities of the board of directors (supervisory board) members and the board of directors (supervisory board) of top managers, a number of companies have developed annual surveys. In other companies, this information is collected at annual meetings by discussing the activities of the board of directors (supervisory board) and its effectiveness in the previous year.

Research methodology

Another common way to assess the activities of the board of directors (supervisory board) abroad is through an individual interview, usually conducted through open questions by the chairman of the remuneration committee. Written surveys are considered more meaningful in terms of completeness and quality of information.

In the field of methodology for assessing the effectiveness of the board of directors (supervisory board) in companies, Russia is one of the leading CIS countries. Realizing the importance of evaluating the activities of the board of directors (supervisory board), Russian companies are developing and improving methods of assessment.

The experience of the Russian Institute of directors (RID, Russia) shows that in order to better analyze the activities of the board of directors (supervisory board), it is advisable to jointly use subjective self-assessment (questionnaires, interviews) and

objective assessment (by analyzing the internal documents of the company) by its members.

Results

In general, according to the results of the analysis of its international practice, 5 methods can be distinguished for assessing the effective performance of members of the board of directors (supervisory board). They are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Methods used to assess the effectiveness of the activities of members of the board of directors (supervisory board)

It should be noted that in recent years, it is the 5th method that is, the creation of integrated software products, which includes the possibilities of interviews, questionnaires and analysis of documents and results, is of paramount importance. Because through this software product, it leads to the optimization of the process of assessing the effectiveness of the activities of the members of the supervisory board at their enterprises with state participation, that is, the time required to prepare, conduct and complete this assessment, financial and labor and other resources are saved.

Conclusion

In conclusion, work on assessing the effectiveness of the activities of members of the supervisory board at state-owned enterprises operating in our republic is not carried out. Because in this regard, methodological development and mechanisms for its implementation have not been developed. Taking into account this, it is advisable to first develop a methodology for assessing the effectiveness of the activities of members of the supervisory board at state enterprises using advanced foreign practices, and to create software products in this regard.

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